

The limits of the photographic act as a metaphor for the assessment of organizational culture. An ethnographic study of a High Reliability Organization

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Abstract

Previous research on organizational culture has mainly adopted a realistic approach when describing organizations' culture. Nonetheless, this approach does not take into consideration relevant factors that influence the process of describing and analyzing organizational culture. This study aims to discuss about critical aspects that conform organizational culture assessment methodologies. It offers a thick description (Geertz, 1973) of the organizational processes that underlie the design and development of the study of the culture of high reliability organizations using a social constructionist perspective (Gergen, 1985). More specifically, an ethnographic study using the metaphor of the assessment of organizational culture as a photographic act (snapshot) of culture in a given moment was carried out. The analysis showed some of the aspects that are taken for granted and are hidden within the metaphor of the photographic act, such as the choice of photographic device (the specific type of assessment techniques used), the framing and focus (the actors allowed in the photo and who will give voice to the culture involved) and the photo processing lab (the type of analysis and interpretation done on the data collected). These elements are important conditioners that make it possible to establish a presumably true image (a specific narrative) of organizational culture.

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1. Introduction:

To date, research on how to capture and describe organizational culture in high reliability organizations have captured researchers and practitioners' attention. It is necessary to point out that the hegemonic approach of studies focusing on culture in high reliability organizations (hereafter HRO) is a historical consequence of risk and safety analysis evolution that has developed significantly over the last few years (Le Coze, 2008; Leveson, 2011; Wahlström, 2011). Recent studies reveal the need to avoid oversimplified assumptions and perspectives based on a merely technological concept of safety (Hopkins, 2006). Organizational theory has shown that organizational and cultural aspects are crucial in the achievement of safety and efficiency in technologically-complex systems (Richardson, 1995; Vaughan, 1996; Medvedev, 1991). Research has also revealed that organizational culture and safety culture are inextricably linked (Guldenmund, 2000).

At this point, one must review the idea of "culture", a word with very different meanings used in a variety of ways. Its definition in the literature is based on multiple suppositions and a variety of theoretical perspectives. Some of the definitions that are most often cited refer to behavioral rules and cognitions (Lehman, Chiu, & Schaller, 2004); values, beliefs and underlying assumptions (Schein, 1992); and the way people think and behave in relation to others and to their duties and responsibilities (Cooke & Lafferty, 1986). From a functionalist perspective or a realistic approach, organizational culture has been used principally in the mainstream literature on organizations as something which is to be measured (assessed) and managed (improved) in order to achieve organizational efficiency.

Along these lines, it is interesting to point out how the concept of safety culture emerging from the accident at Chernobyl has evolved in time. The technical documentation developed by the IAEA have transformed a concept initially based on "universal features" (IAEA, 1991) into another concept in which culture is considered a process based on organizational practices (IAEA, 1998). In turn, this concept becomes a more operative idea of safety culture based on attributes and indicators (IAEAa, 2002). In this way safety culture is expected to be measure, monitored and managed.

Nonetheless, organizational culture is a complex concept difficult to capture in simple, direct terms. Authors such as Smircich (1983) and Martin (2001), among others, have highlighted other theoretical frameworks. These are based on ontological assumptions and consequences differing from those based on traditional organizational culture approaches.

Hence, the present study takes a critical approach to the study of organizational and safety culture by focusing on the processes that make it possible to describe and understand an organization's culture. This study pretends to explore some of the aspects that influence the process of describing and analyzing organizational and safety culture. We specifically attempt to show, through an ethnographic study, the local processes and micro-social practices that contribute to the configuration (in a high risk organization) of what could be called a "method of evaluation" for the diagnosis of organizational culture.

With the aim of clarifying the perspective of our ethnographic study, we will firstly present various theoretical approaches that could be placed between the realistic and social constructionist perspectives. This study takes on a social constructionist approach. Secondly, we will discuss the possibilities of applying ethnographic research to study the culture of high reliability organizations. Thirdly, the "photographic act" metaphor is presented as an implicit idea widely used in the literature on culture and in the safety culture assessments. The idea of the "photographic act" metaphor will be used as a basis for presenting the results of our qualitative analysis. Lastly, as a summary, we will point out some significant differences between the way in which the realistic and social constructionist perspectives approach the study of safety culture.

1.1. Diverse perspectives to the study of culture

The following are some of the theoretical frameworks taken into consideration in the study of organizational culture.

Guldenmund (2000) identifies three approaches to the study of safety culture. The academic approach views culture as the result of the past and determines what the organization "is" in the present. This approach is primarily searching for meaning and interpretation. In order to understand culture qualitative methods of social research would be needed (e. g., ethnography). Then there is the analytical approach which sees culture as something that an organization "has" (and that can be transformed or changed) and focuses in the organizations' present. This concept is based on a multidimensional construct that allows for the quantification, ordering and classification of different cultures. Finally, there is the pragmatic approach which emphasizes how structure, procedures and culture interact, generating a specific organizational result which can influence performance. This approach establishes desired behaviors and its final goal is leading the organization to this desirable future state.

Each one of these perspectives is based on different concepts of what culture is and of how its study should be approached. The different approaches could be placed somewhere between the realistic and social constructionist perspectives on the study of safety culture.

This study attempts to explain how the choice of a particular perspective conditions the study of culture. It is noted that the academic approach, as opposed to the analytical and pragmatic approaches, does not attempt to quantify culture but to put on the table the fact that describing the culture of an organization implies an interpretation of reality. It could be said that the academic approach is more similar to a social constructionist perspective, whereas the analytical and pragmatic approaches are more like the realistic perspective. This study adopts a social constructionist perspective, questioning the very process underlying the study of culture and its methodological deployment. The perspective of Martin (2001), Gergen (1996), as well as the application of theories of power and their relationship with the study of culture (Antonsen, 2009), help us to analyze this aspect in detail.

The classification developed by Martin (2001), based on the work done by Chia (1996) also merits mention. Martin identifies two approaches: 'being/realism' and 'becoming realism'. The 'being-realism' approach sees the world as comprised of identifiable materials and social entities that exist independently of observation and that can be represented concisely through language. This approach treats the concepts of "organization" and "culture" as objects of unproblematic analysis as if their ontological status was not in and of itself a critical aspect. This leads to the reification of culture as something external that exists objectively and cannot be challenged due to the enormous amount of empirical evidence that supports its existence.

The 'becoming-realism' perspective focuses on the process of becoming, on how things come to be. In the study of organizational culture, words, categories and concepts would be used to construct ideas, modify meaning, hide ambiguities and contradictions and avoid problems and uncertainty. According to the becoming-realism approach, there are different ways of writing about culture that are used to highlight the inevitable uncertainties of the conceptualization and writing processes. These writing strategies attempt to reflect the ambiguities of the becoming-realism approach inherent in the study and representation of cultural materials (Clifford and Markus 1986).

Studies on the becoming-realism approach fall within a social constructionist perspective. Social constructionism questions inherited truths and points out the historical and cultural specificity of knowledge. According to Gergen (1985, p.1) "*Social constructionist inquiry is principally concerned with explicating the processes by which people come to describe, explain, or otherwise account for the world (...) in which they live.*"

From a social constructionist perspective, organizational culture is a collective process that is found, negotiated, generated and transplanted in a specific historical context (Gergen 1996). In the study of organizational culture, “the elaboration of the micro-social processes on which scientific knowledge is based” (Gergen, 1996, p.66) is particularly important. As Gherardi (2006) points out, from a micro-social perspective, the practices that occur in different action contexts show the inner workings of social, material and symbolic processes. Several authors have described the nature and dynamics of ‘culture’ and its social construction, illustrating the social and interactive character of organizations (Reinman and Oedewald, 2007; Orr, 1996; Rochlin, 1999; Bourrier, 1999; Gherardi and Nicolini, 2002; Hutchins, 1995).

Similarly, a number of authors have revealed the role of power in organizations and its relationship with the way in which culture itself is built (Perrow, 1999; Antonsen 2009). Power relations affect the way in which culture is shaped and vice versa. In short:

“The strength of power based approaches lies in their emphasis on questions regarding whose interests organizations serve. Organizational culture is never politically neutral, but is likely to be biased in reflecting the values and world-views of dominant groups in the organization” (Antonsen, 2009: 187)

The implications of all this for the evaluation process are clear. The study of culture and its methodological deployment are not free from the influence of power relations. The presence of power relations (which are not always visible) significantly limits and conditions the assumptions of what culture, method, data-gathering techniques, information analysis and the very purpose of the study are. In other words, decisions and “non decisions” (Luke, 1974) determine which alternatives are rendered feasible and which are not even considered when deciding or discussing how to assess the culture of a particular organization.

1.2. Organizational culture and ethnographic research

This study looks at the processes and micro-social practices intervening in the study of organizational culture. To do that, an ethnographic study of the process is undertaken, questioning its objective nature and considering the role of power relations.

The term ‘ethnographic research’ refers to a methodological process originating in social anthropology in which a holistic understanding of the object of study is developed (DeWalt and DeWalt, 2002). In this case, the study subject is the process that make it possible to describe and understand organizational culture. Studies of this type are based principally on field work. In ethnographic studies it is assumed that data needs to be interpreted so that context information is crucial. Thus, ethnographic studies make it possible to discover disparate and evolving relationships between diverse entities, be they material, symbolic or social, objective or subjective, or human or non-human (Serres, 1994).

For instance, the use of ethnography as a ‘methodological procedure’ makes it possible to obtain a thick description of culture, with culture being understood as the context in which social processes are inscribed. According to Geertz (1973):

“As interworked systems of construable signs (what, ignoring provincial usages, I would call symbols), culture is not a power, something to which social events, behaviors, institutions or processes can be causally attributed; it is a context, something within which they can be intelligibly –that is, thickly- described” (p.14)

From this perspective, ethnography as a methodology basically makes reference to research based on field work. Field work is the identifying characteristic of the ethnographic method. As Velasco and Díaz de Rada (1997) point out, it is as much a methodological situation as a research process *per se*.

There are a number of recent studies that have used the ethnographic method to study organizational and safety culture in high reliability organizations (HROs). The debate between the theory of high reliability and NAT (Normal Accident Theory), together with Man Made Disaster Theory (La Porte and Consolini, 1991; Schulman, 1993, Weick and Sutcliffe, 2001, Turner and Pidgeon, 1997; Gherardi and Nicolini, 2002) contributed to the acceptance of ethnographic research for the study of safety. One of the most significant outcomes of the heated NAT- HRO theory debate was the visibility ethnographic studies in HROs gained. There are now case studies that cover all of the different sectors and organizations that are considered high risk. A list of examples, which is by no means exhaustive, includes ethnographic research in organizations in the nuclear sector (Weick, 1979; Schulman, 1993); in the study of accidents (Vaughan, 1996, Le Coze, 2008); in health care in order to improve patient safety (Dixon-Woods et al., 2009) or to increase emergency system resilience (Tveiten et al., 2012); and in the aeronautics industry (Atak and Kingma, 2011).

It is also worth mentioning that the heterogeneity of these ethnographic studies has produced a wide range of epistemological approaches. Thus it is possible to find ethnographic studies aimed at validating a scientific model for work safety practices (Høyland, 2012) or studies that use a social constructionist approach to question the concept of technology-based safety culture (Perin, 2006; Bourrier, 2011).

In fact, prior ethnographic research has called into question the technological approach to safety, pointing out that safety and reliability in organizations are not simply the result of good technology in combination with appropriate culture, but also of an appropriate organizational design. In other words, *“choices are made, allocations are decided and these do greatly influence the potential to be simply safe and reliable”* (Bourrier, 2011). Bourrier goes on to state that ethnographic studies contribute to an understanding of to what extent safety is the result of social and technological processes. In his words (Bourrier, 2011):

“We know so little about the functioning of complex organizations. We are only looking at the top of the iceberg. Deep below, complex work is done, people are toiling, and complex decisions are made every day, with few paying attention to them. We depend on these invisible webs of teams, decisions, technology, infrastructure, and yet we know almost nothing about their daily operations” (p.12).

1.3. The metaphor of photographic act

The “photographic act” metaphor will be used as a basis for presenting the results of this study for several reasons. Firstly, it is important to emphasize that this metaphor is implicit in the perspective of some international agencies in the field of safety culture. That means the comparison of a picture is used to refer to the final result of a safety culture assessment (Health and Safety Executive, 2005; IAEAa, 2002; IAEA b, 2002).

The photographic act comparison as an equivalent of the evaluation process has gained such relevance that at times it has been used by governmental agencies (e.g., New Zealand Ministry of Business, 2012; U.S. Department of Energy Office of Environmental Management Headquarters, 2012).

Secondly, as previously mentioned, an analytical approach to the study of organizational and safety culture assumes that the result obtained through an assessment process is a snapshot of a particular organization: *“the analytical approach provides a current snapshot of a culture and, because of its (quasi-) numerical assessment, a means for ordering cultures”* (Guldenmund, 2010: 1476). That means that an evaluation is expected to offer a ‘point in time’ snapshot. In the same vein, other authors will consider assessment results *“in terms of the immediate identification of potential safety issues”* (Jacobs & Haber, 1994).

Finally, in the academic world, the term snapshot has also been used to refer to safety climate. Along these lines, Denison (1996) points out that climate is an “ahistorical snapshot” (Denison, 1996), meaning it only refers to the present, without any historical reference. Similarly, other authors (Flin et al., 2000; Mearns, et al., 1997) say that safety climate is a manifestation or “snapshot” of the safety culture. That would mean a safety climate study can only provide a partial, superficial image of an organization's safety culture in a given moment (Cox and Flin, 1998).

It is important to mention that the use of the photographic image metaphor has significant implications in terms of the nature of the study. To put it another way, the acceptance of evaluation results as a snapshot entails accepting a realistic perspective in the study of culture. That means it would be considered objective and valid, regardless of the measurement techniques used. Culture exists so it should be visualized somehow. It also implies assuming that the use of evaluation techniques provides a single, clear image showing an indisputable organizational reality. Thus, using the photographic image metaphor implies assuming a realistic approach.

With the aim of facilitating understanding of the different approaches to the study of culture, the following table compares the realistic and social constructionist perspectives. The intend of this table is not to be thorough but to illustrate the key differences between the two perspectives as well as their implications in the evaluation processes.

	Realistic approach	Social constructionist approach
Object of study: Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critical component of the organization. - Determined mainly by organizational leaders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is a collective process - It is negotiated, generated and transplanted in a particular organization
Purpose of the assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of essential culture characteristics - Getting a Snapshot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Favoring understanding of social processes and practices on which culture is embedded
Methodological deployment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The methodology is an indisputable aspect - Predominance of quantitative techniques - The use of complementary qualitative techniques is admitted to make the image clearer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The method as a socially-built aspect - Use of qualitative techniques to understand culture
Analyzing and obtaining evaluation results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results emerge clearly and naturally from the data - Aspects related to the issue of power excluded from evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The results are mediated by the interpretations of researchers - Power relations as inherent aspect in the evaluation process.
The role of the researcher - evaluator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researcher is an expert that applies techniques accurately. - The researcher simply gathers information and then lets "the data do the talking". There is no room for interpretation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The influence of the researcher in the object of study must be taken into consideration (reflexivity). - Interpretation as a key element to analyze data

Fig. 1. Realistic versus socio-constructionist approach.

2. Methodology

2.1. Aim of the analysis and epistemological approach

This study aims at providing a thick description of the organizational processes underpinning the design of an organizational culture evaluation in a high reliability organization. We intend to understand how practices and activities intertwine in an organization to portrait an 'image' of the organizational culture. In other words, we intend to understand the process for establishing a set of rules and assessment activities that comprise the 'assessment methodology' and how they influence the presumably true image of organizational culture.

Along these lines, we also understand that the findings of a methodology are not only the results of what we may call the true culture, but also the result of a social process that modifies and alters that culture. This instrument – the methodology – is the product of a complex web of interests, power relationships, and interactions between a set of actors struggling to achieve specific objectives. Thus, in our study we intend to question, from a non-representational perspective, the notion of 'assessment methodology' understood as the mere application of a set of research techniques in accordance with the assumptions of the snapshot metaphor. In our analysis we will show that what is normally called 'assessment methodology' is actually a complex process of negotiation emerging from the micro-social interaction of multiple social actors. The results of this process determine the form and possibilities of the so-called organizational culture.

As part of our safety culture assessment, we put together a field diary comprising the processes that intervene in the structuring of a method for assessing culture. As will be commented later, the field diary was created by a team of researchers participating in the organizational and safety culture evaluation of an HRO. This study focuses on the processes underlying the design of a culture evaluation study, without going into evaluation results. We acknowledge that it is important to know the processes that articulate assessment practices (which, when taken together, constitute the methodology) because the application of these practices will provide a specific image or narrative of the organizational culture.

2.2. Field notes and organizational context

As stated in the preceding point, this study focuses on a qualitative analysis of the ethnographic field diary put together by a team of researchers during the organizational culture assessment. That means, as above mentioned, that evaluation results will not be discussed. In order to contextualize analysis results, we present the following information on the type of organizational evaluation developed and the criteria used to make the field diary.

The organization Tecnela –fictitious business name-, operating in the energy sector, undertook this study as part of a process aimed at improving and strengthening its organizational and safety culture. For Tecnela this organizational culture assessment was a significant first step in the field of safety culture. Tecnela asked to our research unit (UIS) to design and implement an organizational culture assessment using a pragmatic approach (Guldenmund, 2000). The evaluation used several research techniques that were both quantitative (questionnaires) and qualitative (interviews and focus groups). The evaluation resulted in a diagnostic report pointing, among other things, to a number of organizational strengths and weaknesses aimed at structuring and developing a safety culture improvement plan. It is also important to mention that from the very moment the evaluation was requested, a collective field diary was developed jointly by the five professionals in our research unit participating in the organizational culture evaluation of Tecnela.

The main purpose guiding the elaboration of the field diary -during the assessment- was to obtain basic materials that could complement the organizational culture analysis of Tecnela. Specifically, it covers the entire organizational culture evaluation process, including information related to all the evaluation process stages: behind-the-scene discussion on the scope of the evaluation, qualitative and quantitative data-gathering process (surveys and focus groups), data analysis and presentation of results.

As it is known, one of the paradigms of classical ethnography was the need for the researcher to spend long periods of time in the social space under study to ensure symbolic understanding of its social practices. However, the role we played in this project did not allow us to do that. In any case, and as stated by Íñiguez (2006), it could be considered that we have carried out an ethnographic study (or quasi ethnography) because the basic ethnography assumptions were fulfilled: the study of human behaviors took place in their natural environments and knowledge of social behaviors took into consideration the "symbolic world" of the study subjects. In line with the theories of Hammersley and Atkinson (1994), the preparation of our field diary intended to systematically optimize our participation and stay as researchers in the settings included in the study so as to produce a 'valid' story on the social world of the organization.

The ethnographic research was developed over a period of 18 months. The process begins the very moment our research center receives the request for an organizational culture evaluation, and it ends when evaluation results are presented in various work sessions. The diary registers interactions between our researchers and the organization from the moment when the evaluation was initially developed until the results were presented. It also includes the information considered relevant and susceptible of providing culture-related information. For illustrative purposes, we show some of the diary entries comprising the work analysis material.

"The management committee has not authorized project launching yet. (...). Unless there are last-minute changes, it seems there will no problems to implement the original plan with just a few modifications"

"Plant tour, XX in department R2 says repeatedly that people do not know that radioactivity can be eliminated with a little cloth"

"At the end of the presentation [of results], the Q&A session starts. One of the questions caused some controversy (...); someone wanted to know if the sites had the same culture (...)"

Although a wide variety of observations were included in the diary, it is necessary to make some remarks. The basic criteria for recording information in the field notes were established. It was also decided that whenever possible, one basic criterion for writing information in the diary was the separation between descriptive, factual information and evaluative information (i.e. researchers' work hypothesis on the organizational culture at Tecnela, private reflections, etc.). An example of evaluative information included in the field diary is shown.

"I travel thinking that there is a brand new world to discover at Tecnela, that something is going to happen. But all this happens very subtlety. A visit and a focus group help me adjust my vision, but do not really provide me with the information needed to go a step further"

One of the team researchers was in charge of managing the information recorded in the diary. All of it, the field diary and the reference material, such as notes on focus groups, minutes and safety culture team reports, comprised the corpus of data collected and analyzed for this study. Many entries in the field diary took place *in situ* due to the nature of social interactions.

Manual and electronic means were used to record the observations made during the different work meetings.

2.3. Analysis of the field diary

According to the objectives of this study, research aspects guiding the field diary data analysis process were mainly the following: a) Identification of the main processes and organizational factors related to the organizational culture evaluation process; b) Interests and influence of the different agents in the evaluation process; c) Relationship between the different experts and their influence in the selection of a methodological procedure.

The analysis was done from a critical, constructionist perspective, which determines that language must be conceived as a social practice and builder of realities (Garay, Íñiguez and Martínez 2005; Edwards and Potter 2005). Simple coding procedures were used to categorize the field notes. Furthermore, categories were used to interpret the organizational process. With this discourse analysis in mind, the aim is to facilitate understanding of complex organizational processes emerging from an organizational culture evaluation. Furthermore, the field diary was analyzed in a way that ensured confidentiality and anonymity, both of the organization and informants.

3. Results

The main findings of the field diary analysis are included below, using the snapshot metaphor as a structuring element for presenting the analysis. This metaphor is implicit in realistic methodologies, which are hegemonic in organizational culture analyses. According to this paradigm, results emerge clean and naturally from the data, rendering a 'photographic image' of the organizational culture in a given moment. The social constructionism approach adopted in this study questions the validity of the metaphor because it omits processes that are part of the actual analysis such as interpretation. In other words, we assume the idea that a picture requires a narration for their understanding; only the language is capable of describing (Sontag, 1977).

The snapshot metaphor allow us, firstly, to illustrate the interdependence between the ethnographic text and the qualitative analysis (Hammersley and Atkinson, 1994), showing continuity and coherence with the metaphors used and the concepts addressed (Lofland and Lofland, 1984). Secondly, it is useful to identify the different processes underlying evaluation methodology design. The organization members influence the photographic image through their decisions, such as selection of the 'photographic' instrument, zoom, focus/setting, and even the development lab (meaning the information analysis and interpretation strategies that render an accurate image of organizational culture). We intend to illustrate those aspects that are usually ignored when organizational culture evaluation processes are considered from a 'naturalized' perspective. In short, the idea is to underline the existence of a comprehensive set of factors conditioning the evaluation and largely determining the feasibility of the actual evaluation process.

The analysis has been structured based on the following aspects:

- Setting: photographing (a part of) the organization
- The photographic instrument: The main camera and other lenses
- The development lab: battling for the resulting image

3.1. Setting: photographing (a part of) the organization

"Setting: the act of capturing an external reality by choosing and organizing the elements that will be part of the image; in other words, the elements included in the photograph and the scene portion to be captured by the photographer" (Wikipedia)

In this first section we present the organization evaluated, as well as the different members that participated actively in the organizational culture evaluation process. The organization, Tecnela, is a HRO in the energy sector, leader in its field of production. Tecnela put together a working group with the formal objective of improving organizational and safety culture, although there was another relevant underlying driver: the need to comply with specific requirements of the regulatory body in the field of safety culture.

It is important to mention that the work group in charge of enhancing safety culture was an instrument created by the board of directors so as to properly manage compliance with the regulatory requirements.

One of the initial lines of work established by the organizational culture team, as recommended by two consultancy firms (Proton and UIS), was the need for an organizational culture evaluation to establish a baseline. The main focus of the evaluation was to obtain specific knowledge on the organizational culture of Tecnela. The evaluation process included a full set of group decisions, meaning the work team had to make important decisions that marked the setting of the organizational culture image. One of the decisions of the safety

culture team was to establish the participation criteria for the organizational groups in the evaluation: a comprehensive selection process (screening) to determine which organization members were going to be represented in the organizational culture image and which were not. It is obvious that deciding who can and cannot "voice" their opinion on the organizational culture clearly determines the accuracy of the photographic 'image'. Thus, the participation (or not) of some contractors determined the meaning of organization membership in this case.

"The participation of contractors at the Corporate Headquarters was discussed at length. My impression is that some group members feel the participation of contractors may make the culture photograph a little "blurry". The group in general seems to accept that people in the VR unit, and XY should participate, but not the cleaning personnel."

The inclusion / exclusion of contractors in the organizational culture evaluation process was defined by the most powerful members in the safety culture group. These members laid down the acceptability and participation criteria (*"we depend on the decision of the group leaders, who will most likely limit contractors participation as much as possible"*). Needless to say, the inclusion/exclusion process was overshadowed in the "2011 overview report" informing Tecnela management on project status:

"Surveys have been given to all the staff in the different work centers, as well as to a large number of permanent contractors"

The decision to allow participation in the evaluation was crucial and certainly not naive. In fact, our field diary includes some events occurring during the organizational culture evaluation that help to clarify the meaning of the word "employee" in this organization. Those events point to a constant dichotomy in Tecnela: "organization employee" versus "contractor" or, in other words "first-class employee" versus "second-class employee". This distinction has significant implications in the daily life of this business organization. In the words of a contractor, *"our clothes are stained with oil, dust, etc, (...) but they won't wash them for us; we have to take our clothes home to get them clean"*. The framing chosen by the organization intended to prevent these photographic gray areas from being seen.

There were more aspects in this process that influenced the photographic framing, such as the moment chosen to conduct the study. In relation to the time chosen to distribute the survey, some team members pointed out that *"[The data-gathering plan for this site] is still subject to change since they are in the middle of negotiating a labor agreement and we have to make sure the surveys do not interfere"*. This was a clear example of how activities undertaken by the organization influenced the moment chosen for capturing the photographic image.

Finally, there were other relevant questions that seemed to impact the actual framing, such as the perception of how useful the process is. In other words, the way in which organization members viewed the process in some cases seemed to condition their voluntary participation and inclusion in the organizational culture image setting. Some opinions obtained while distributing the surveys were a good example of that: *"I don't know why they want us to answer; they're going to ignore us after all"*.

3.2. The photographic instrument: The main camera and other lenses

"Photographers control the camera and lens to "expose" the light recording material (such as film) to the required amount of light to form a "latent image" or "raw file" (...) after appropriate processing, is converted to a usable image" (Wikipedia)

The following section illustrates some of the processes taking place in the organization to select the organizational culture evaluation instruments. It shows how the interests of some

organizational stakeholders determine the inclusion of specific measurement questionnaires with the aim of instrumentalizing results (to use the image). On the one hand, some of the key stakeholders included the Tecnela work team and a number of external organizational and safety culture experts. It is also worth mentioning that current safety regulations conditioned the study undertaken.

Tecnela's work team was comprised of people with a high level of responsibility in the organization. The team suggested the need to undertake an organizational culture study *"using common methods and tools of specific interest in the area of culture"*. The objective of this suggestion was to present an "objective" image of the organizational culture that could comply with specific safety regulation requirements. To do that, it was proposed to follow studies already carried out in similar organizations.

It is important to point out that the application of specific research techniques and especially their theoretical framework, condition the resulting image. On the other hand, analysis of field diary processes showed that the "objectivity" of these theoretical models and research techniques was justified simply because they had previously been used in other organizations to meet specific safety regulations in the same type of installations.

Similarly, the selection of research techniques and instruments was also conditioned by the need to satisfy other important objectives of the organization. In this regard and as requested by the staff management department, a new survey was included, that is to say, an additional "photographic instrument". The idea behind this new survey was to provide information on the development of staff management over the last few years (*"to compare with the climate survey conducted 11 years ago"*). The purpose was to obtain proof that the department had managed staff effectively. In words of a staff manager collaborator *"he is doing it for political purposes, I mean, he wants to take credit for enhancing changes"*. The survey included sensitive evaluative aspects, such as questions related to staff opinions regarding senior management performance and wages.

Paradoxically, organization employees, especially in the corporate headquarters, ended up associating the culture evaluation process to the staff management department. Thus, the field diary showed employee comments made after the survey was filled out: *"Why do they call it culture when they mean sex? Because it refers to a topic of interest for human resources."* This association resulted in enormous distrust regarding the aim of the entire process.

3.3. The development lab: battling for the resulting image

"Photographic processing (...) transforms the latent image into a visible image, makes this permanent and renders it insensitive to light." (Wikipedia)

The third aspect of the analysis is related to negotiations between stakeholders regarding data analysis and dissemination. Prior to using diary fragments to illustrate relevant process aspects, we will make a brief presentation of the consultancy firms providing technical support to Tecnela in the field of safety and culture. The first company (Proton) was specialized in the field of in HRO. This consulting firm facilitated the participation of the second consulting company (UIS): a public research agency with experience in organizational and safety culture evaluations in the energy sector.

The diary revealed how a relationship initially conceived to be complementary and collaborative, eventually turned into a rather competitive and unfriendly relation. There are numerous examples that clearly show the progressive deterioration of their relationship when both consultancy teams met in Tecnela:

"I arrived to the Mr. XP's office at the 10:00. They were already with XX and YY. The session was adjourned immediately. Handshakes. Mr. XP and Mr. XX acted out a bit, but not Mr. YY, who seemed haughty and offended".

Analysis of the field diary reveals that the main divergence between Proton and UIS revolved around their battle to gain legitimacy before the members of Tecnela when presenting the results. In fact, it could be said that the efforts of both organizations to establish themselves as legitimate hermeneutics of Tecnela's was at the very root of their conflict, which eventually resulted in the end of their somewhat collaborative relationship. Although competition between Proton and UIS seemed to be the result of technical or interpretative aspects, the underlying factor was the "business" interest that both organizations had in the project. There were a number of "methodological" implications indicating that both organizations would be competing to be awarded future organizational and safety culture evaluations of other HRO in the energy sector.

It is paradoxical in this context to note that although the functions of both organizations were "aseptically" described as technical advisors for Tecnela, which was in the process of adapting to the requirements put forward by the regulatory body (in words of an organization member *"it was decided to contract out specialized technical support and consultancy services"*), the field diary shows that the private interests of each organization (both *Proton* and *UIS*) eventually influenced the design of the organizational culture evaluation significantly. In other words, the private interests of Proton and UIS ended up defining not only key aspects such as the selection of evaluation instruments (i.e. specific organizational culture questionnaire and focus group protocol) but also critical methodological aspects, such as the type of data analysis and even the result interpretation approach. To put it differently, they influenced the photography development process and the creation of the message chosen to disseminate evaluation results.

Various analysis strategies were selected. On the one hand, questionnaire results were completed with information from meetings, informal interviews, and focus groups. The existence of subcultures trying to claim their idiosyncrasy was emphasized. The objective of this strategy was to carry out a detailed description of the organizational and safety culture under analysis. On the other hand, a comparative study intended to interpret the image obtained was undertaken, taking as reference the results obtained in prior studies both nationally and internationally. The reference frameworks adopted resulted in different photographic images. In this particular case, the final image is a graphic representation in the shape of a circular diagram. After analyzing the different images, it was determined that some provided additional information whereas others were contradictory.

As for experts, they were not only interested in offering technical advice, but in providing an accurate image of the organization. That was the case of UIS experts. Paradoxically, that meant that Tecnela's culture image was going to be more blurry and unclear as a result of the complexity of its organizational culture. For Proton experts, the development process was a test bench that could be useful for future studies. Similarly, it could lay the foundations for future interventions in projects related to organizational change and development.

As for the Tecnela work group, their aim was to obtain one single photograph, sharp and clear. It was not so much about the value of the photographic image (evaluation results) but about being able to justify the actual photograph. In words of a work group member *"if we continue performing rigorously, we will have the acceptability of the regulatory body"*.

The scarce value of the methodological dispute (in other words, the discussion on the scientific validity of the organizational culture image) is illustrated by the notes written in the field diary the day that the Tecnela culture team leader presented the organizational culture evaluation results to senior management. For the team leader (Mr. XP) *"the most important thing about*

these results is that they show the need to work, to continue working". A "presentation of results without results" or a photography exhibition without photographs. The most interesting thing about this is that the observer said that nobody in the senior management team seemed surprised:

"Another idea that came to me during the presentation of the results is that everything seemed to be a Goffman-style theater play. The truth is that there is a reason why in spite of obtaining no results, nobody raises the question of where the missing results are: behind the scenes and prior to Mr. XP presentation, everyone received a documentation package with the results." In other words, everyone knows the results that they pretend not to know and to be listening to... listening to a presentation of results without results. Nobody says anything because Mr. XP has already distributed the results, probably tailored made, for every single Tom, Dick and Harry in senior management"

However, if the field diary is taken into consideration, it could be said that Mr. XP's presentation included significant organizational messages and results, such as *"results are worse in the lower hierarchical levels"*. During the presentation, there was also a recommendation entailing important future implications. The recommendation, based on comparisons with previous reports (also by Proton), suggested the need to continue working with Proton because *"if your company is compared with the best sector companies included in our international database, then it is not doing so well"*. All this, under the umbrella of compliance with regulatory body requirements.

4. Discussion

As previously mentioned, the purpose of this study was to explore some of the aspects that influence the process of describing and analyzing organizational culture. This exploration was done through a socio-constructionist approach. More specifically, the researchers used an ethnographic study focused on the local processes and micro-social practices that contribute to the configuration of a "method of evaluation" applied to the organizational culture. The results of this study reveal the limits of the realistic paradigm through the metaphor of the photographic act. By comparing the assessment process to a snapshot, a number of epistemological and ontological assumptions on the purpose of the study and its evaluation method were made. One of these assumptions implied rendering as valid the idea that the final evaluation product is exactly the same as the object of the study. However, our analysis shows that the "method of evaluation" and the results obtained through it, derive from a negotiation process between the different actors involved. Procedures, activities and techniques used to describe the object of study (culture) are not, let's say, natural. Therefore, the method of evaluation eventually enables but also limits the possibilities of the actual photographic act. Besides, the results show that the "method of evaluation" does not only enable culture representation, but it is also a product somewhat conditioned by the very culture of the organization.

The results of this study have significant theoretical implications in the field of organizational culture. In line with some authors (Chia, 1996; Smircich, 1983; Martin, 2001), the very existence of organizational culture as an external object of study that can be assessed objectively without any bias, is put into question. Similarly, in line with the 'becoming realism' perspective (e.g., Martin, 2001), it would be possible to question normative models attempting to describe the organizational culture of an organization. In relation to culture assessment processes, it implies that the methodology of evaluation cannot be conceived as an immune, independent object in its genesis to social organizational processes that ends up providing an accurate, objective representation of the characteristics defining the organizational culture. That means that the realistic paradigm is questioned and that some of the axioms of the social-constructionist perspective are reinforced. This last approach acknowledges the daily nature of science-building, to such an extent that it can actually be conceived as a social activity similar to other activities, and where the senses are socially built through negotiation (Spink, 2003). In the words of Ibáñez (1994):

"To present the social reality, to rigorously understand its very nature, both at an ontological level and at a knowledge-based level. The key to do this is elucidation, which implies that it is important to pay attention to the means for building, producing, reproducing and transforming that social reality, with special focus on the behaviors and actions of the social agents" (p. 147, 148)

This study also shows the relevance of taking into consideration the issue of power when studying the organizational culture of HROs. This perspective takes a critical look at processes underlying the design of any organizational culture study, the selection of the study methodology, and the analysis of the results obtained. Seemingly, a number of authors pointed out the need of including a power-orientated perspective in future organizational culture assessments (Antonsen, 2009; Perrow, 1999).

Lastly, ethnographic research reveals itself as a very useful way to approach this topic. In this study we attempted to put the methodology configuring process at the very core of the analysis, as an object for ethnographic study. That is, all the practices and interactions including the definition and scope of the evaluation, the application of research techniques - both quantitative and qualitative -, and even the act of interpreting the results obtained through the 'evaluation methodology'. In other words, we have undertaken the study of the

method, assuming that the focus is on a group of social activities performed by the organizational actors with different interests and interdependences. These activities eventually result in a particular image of the organizational culture. For instance, the analysis of the field diary at Tecnela shows how the exclusion in the evaluation process of a group of workers (contractors) was organizationally “forgotten” in the process of culture development and result dissemination. The ethnographic study also shows how culture is embodied in a specific graphic representation (circular diagram), and how the communication process shows this graphic representation, which was to be an objective picture of the culture at Tecnela, to the entire organization. Other authors like Vaughan (1996), Le Coze (2008) and Bourrier (2011), among others, have also proven the possibilities and results of applying ethnographic approaches in high reliability organizations.

Regarding practical implications, our analysis reveals that the work of Smircich (1983), Guldenmund (2000), Martin (2001) and Antonsen (2009) help to increase and enrich the possibilities of studying organizational culture, either by indicating the need to adopt a critical vision of organizations or by explaining the implications of the ontological assumptions on which the work is based (Martin, 2001). Therefore, it is useful to keep these aspects in mind before studying organizational culture. Secondly, by assuming that the methodology is actually a result (that is, it is never a natural, systematic or mathematical formula providing indisputable results), then we are somehow putting into perspective and setting limits to the results obtained through its application as an evaluating artifact (or storytelling). This implies the need not only to present the results (the story as an image of the organizational life) but also to specify the factors and peculiarities conditioning the creation of the method itself and, by association, of the culture image presented. It is therefore necessary to reflect on these aspects and to make them explicit so as to the aim of raising awareness on the limitations they entail and adjusting the expectations of the social actors involved in the process.

Thirdly, the conclusions of this study suggest the need to adopt a reflexive, critical perspective that considers the impact of evaluation criteria and techniques on social practices in organizational culture. In other words, it is necessary to present its theories and assumptions, as well as its limits and omissions. Thus, carrying out rigorous organizational culture evaluations must necessarily entail the need to make explicit certain decisions conditioning and guiding the process (from design to result analysis). That calls for the need to include aspects and concepts that usually lie outside the actual discussion. For example, it would be necessary to have information addressing the following questions (these are just an example): What groups are included in the assessment? Why are there groups excluded from the assessment? What criteria determined the use of specific techniques? Which were the analysis criteria? The idea is to incorporate elements favoring critical reflections, which would paradoxically pave the road for questioning the results. We truly believe that safety culture assessments in HRO should clearly mention the implicit assumptions that favored (or hampered) the actions, and that eventually contributed to rendering specific process results. Not mentioning these assumptions, not making them explicit and acknowledging their limiting nature, would result in an evaluation process rendering biased results, and in taking the organizational snapshot as valid and real despite the omission of relevant information. On the contrary, making inherent evaluation context and limits explicit, increases result validity and contributes to developing safer HROs.

Additionally, it is necessary to refer to some limitations of this study. For example, even if our methodology states that the basic principles of ethnographic research were complied with, organization so as to favor understanding of the “symbolic world” related to the object of study. It would also be necessary to rethink the process for ‘normalizing’ ethnographic research as a goal itself, beyond the idea of adopting a pragmatic-based perspective to create a parallel diary in an organizational culture evaluation.

As for upcoming research efforts, ethnography, conceived as an approach to studying organizational culture, opens the door to a number of options, including the possibility to research on the daily negotiations of various agents, to understand how assumptions are made, how limits and exclusions are established, and how everything results in organizational features that have a real, evident nature. Ethnographic studies show how relevant organizational aspects (safety or quality) are *“always playing different roles around power relationships within the organization”* (Íñiguez and Navajas, 2009: 24). Thus, ethnography is a research approach that involves a paused look at the social processes occurring in organizations.

5. Conclusion

This work intended to provide a thick description of the organizational process around an organizational culture assessment.

The analysis showed how social processes inside the organization eventually determine the activities and instruments included in the methodology as well as the specific way in which they are used during the evaluation process. The ethnographic story was structured in three areas of analysis that show some of the main social processes kept apart by the photographic image metaphor. Firstly, our analysis reveals how the inhouse work team created by management establishes the criteria determining the participation or exclusion of some organizational work groups in the evaluation process (external companies). Secondly, the analysis shows the relationship between the interests of some organization stakeholders and the way in which the methodology takes shape, focusing on aspects related to the use and selection of the evaluation instruments, among others. Thirdly, the study presents how data assessment and interpretation processes are not immune to the social processes (power, negotiation and competition) regulating the day to day life of the stakeholders participating in the organizational culture evaluation of Tecnela. Lastly, the article looks at the importance of exposing the underlying aspects (rules of the game) in an evaluation process. These aspects tend to be omitted because they are considered to have a methodological, scientific and incontrovertible nature. However, the ethnographic analysis of Tecnela reveals the social, negotiated nature of these aspects which significantly condition the potential and limits of the actual evaluation product: the story (considered the objective image) of the organization culture.

References

- Antonsen, S., 2009. Safety culture and the issue of power. *Safety science* 47, 183-191.
- Atak, A., Kingma, S., 2011. Safety culture in an aircraft maintenance organization: a view from the inside. *Safety Science* 49, 268-278.
- Bourrier, M., 1999. Constructing organisational reliability: the problem of embeddedness and duality. In: Misumi, J., Wilpert, B., Miller, R. (Eds.), *Nuclear Safety: A Human Factors Perspective*. Taylor & Francis, London, 25–48.
- Bourrier, M., 2011. The legacy of the High Reliability Organizations Project. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management* 19 (1), 9-13.
- Chia, R., 1996. The problem of reflexivity in organisational research: towards a postmodern science of organisation. *Organisation* 3 (1), 31-59.
- Cooke, R.A., Lafferty, J.C., 1986. *Level V: Organizational culture inventory, form III*. Plymouth, MI: Human Synergetics.
- Cox, S., Flin, R., 1998. Safety culture: Philosopher's stone or man of straw?. *Work & Stress*, 12 (3), 189-201.
- Clifford, J., Marcus, G.E., 1986. *Writing Culture: The Poetics and Politics of Ethnography*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Denison, D.R., 1996. What is the difference between organizational culture and organizational climate? A native's point of view on a decade of paradigm wars. *Academy of Management Review*, 21, 619-654.
- DeWalt, K. M., DeWalt, B. R., 2002. *Participant observation: a guide for fieldworkers*. Walnut Creek, CA: AltaMira Press.
- Dixon-Woods, M., Suokas, A., Pitchforth, E., Tarrant, C., 2009. An ethnographic study of classifying and accounting for risk at the sharp end of medical wards. *Social Science and Medicine* 69, 362-269.
- Edwards, D., Potter, J., 2005. Discursive psychology, mental states and descriptions. In H. te Molder & J. Potter (Eds), *Conversation and Cognition*, pp. 241-259. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Flin, R., Mearns, K., O'Connor, P., Bryden, R., 2000. Measuring safety climate: identifying the common features. *Safety Science* 34 (1-3), 177-192.
- Garay, A., Íñiguez, L., Martínez, L.M., 2005. La perspectiva discursiva en psicología social. *Subjetividad y Procesos Cognitivos* 7, 105-130.
- Geertz, C., 1973. *The interpretation of cultures*. Basic books, New York.
- Gergen, K.J., 1985. The Social Constructionist Movement in Modern Psychology. *American Psychologist* 40 (3), 266-275.

Gergen, K.J., 1996. *Realidades y relaciones. Aproximaciones a la construcción social*. Barcelona: Paidós.

Gherardi, S., 2006. *Organizational Knowledge: The Texture of Workplace Learning*. Malden, MA: Blackwell.

Gherardi, S., Nicolini, D., 2002. Learning the trade: a culture of safety in practice. *Organization* 9, 191–223.

Guldenmund, F.W., 2000. The nature of safety culture: a review of theory and research. *Safety Science* 34 (1-3), 215-257.

Guldenmund, F.W., 2010. (Mis)understanding Safety Culture and Its Relationship to Safety Management. *Risk Analysis* 30 (10), 1466-1480.

Hammersley, M., Atkinson, P., 1994. *Etnografía: métodos de investigación*. Edición castellano. Barcelona: Paidós.

Health and Safety Executive, 2005. *The role and effectiveness of safety representatives in influencing workplace health and safety*. UK.

Hopkins, A., 2006. Study organizational cultures and their effects on safety. *Safety Science* 44, 875-889.

Høyland, S., 2012. Developing and validating a scientific model for exploring safe work practices in interdisciplinary teams. *Safety Science* 50 (2), 316-325.

Hutchins, E., 1995. *Cognition in the Wild*. MIT Press, Massachusetts.

IAEA, 1991. *Safety Culture (A Report by the International Nuclear Safety Advisory Group)*, INSAG-4.

IAEA, 1998. *Developing Safety Culture in Nuclear Activities – Practical Suggestions to Assist Progress*, Safety Reports Series No. 11.

IAEAa, 2002. *Key Practical Issues in Strengthening Safety Culture, INSAG-15. Self-Assessment of Safety Culture in Nuclear Installations Highlights and Good Practices*, TECDOC-1321.

IAEAb, 2002. *Key Practical Issues in Strengthening Safety Culture, INSAG-15. Safety Culture in Nuclear Installations: Guidance for Use in the Enhancement of Safety Culture*, TECDOC-1329.

Ibáñez, T., 1994. *Psicología Social Construccionalista. Textos recientes*. Universidad de Guadalajara, México.

Íñiguez, L., 2006. *Análisis del discurso. Manual para las ciencias sociales*. Editorial UOC, Barcelona.

Iñiguez, L., Navajas, J., 2009. *Playing ISO 9:000. Shaping the organization by means of quality*. http://www.academia.edu/1658721/Playing_ISO_9_000_Shaping_the_organization_by_means_of_quality Last access: 26 November 2012.

Jacobs, R., Haber, S., 1994. Organizational processes and nuclear power plant safety. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 45 (1-2), 75-83.

La Porte, T.R., Consolini, P.M., 1991. Working in practice but not in theory: Theoretical challenges of High Reliability Organizations. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 1, 19-47.

Le Coze, J.C., 2008. Disasters and organisations: From lessons learnt to theorising. *Safety Science* 46 (1), 132-149.

Lehman, D.R., Chiu, C., Schaller, M., 2004. Psychology and Culture. *Annual Review of Psychology* 55, 689-714.

Leveson, N.G., 2011. Applying systems thinking to analyze and learn from events. *Safety Science* 49 (1), 55-64.

Lofland, J., Lofland, L., 1984. *Analyzing social settings: A guide to qualitative observation and analysis* (2nd ed.). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.

Luke, S., 1974. *Power: A Radical View*. New York and London: The MacMillan Press, LTD.

Martin, J., 2001. *Organizational culture: Mapping the terrain*. Sage Publications, Incorporated.

Mearns, K., Flin, R., Fleming, M., Gordon, R., 1997. Human and organizational factors, off-shore safety report (OTH 543). Suffolk: HSE Books.

Medvedev, Z., 1991. *El legado de Chernobyl*. Ed. Pomares-Corredor. Barcelona.

New Zealand Ministry of Business, 2012. <http://www.osh.govt.nz/resources/tools/scs/index.shtml> (March 19, 2013).

Orr, J.E., 1996. *Talking about Machines. An Ethnography of a Modern Job*. ILR Press, New York.

Perin, C., 2006. *Shouldering risks: The culture of control in the power nuclear industry*. Princeton University Press.

Perrow, C. 1999. *Normal Accidents with a New 'Afterword'*. Princeton. Princeton University Press.

Reinman, T. and Oedewald, P. (2007). Assessment of complex sociotechnical systems – Theoretical issues concerning the use of organizational culture and organizational core task concepts. *Safety Science* 45 (7), 745-468.

Richardson, B. (1995) Paradox management for crisis avoidance, *Management Decision*, 33 (1): 5-18.

Rochlin, G.I., 1999. Safe operation as a social construct. *Ergonomics* 42, 1549–1560.

Schein, E.H., 1992. *Organizational Culture and Leadership*, second ed. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

Schulman, P.R., 1993. The negotiated order of organizational reliability. *Administration & Society*, 25, 353-72.

Serres, M., 1994. *Eclaircissements, entretiens avec Bruno Latour*. Paris: Flammarion.

Smircich, L., 1983. Concepts of Culture and Organizational Analysis. *Administrative Science Quarterly* 28 (3), 339-358.

Sontag, S., 1977. *On photography*. New York: The Noonday Press.

Spink, M.J., 2003. *Psicologia social e saúde: práticas, saberes e sentidos*. Vozes, Petrópolis.

Turner, B.A., Pidgeon, N.F., 1997. *Man-made disasters*. Second edition. Butterworth-Heinemann, Oxford.

Tveiten, C.K., Albrechtsen E., Wærø, I., Wahl, A.M., 2012. Building resilience into emergency management. *Safety Science* 50, 1960-1966.

U.S. Department of Energy Office of Environmental Management Headquarters, 2012. *Independent Oversight Assessment of Safety Culture at the U.S. Department of Energy of Environmental Management Headquarters*.

Vaughan, D., 1996. *The Challenger launch decision*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Velasco, H., Díaz de Rada, A., 1997. *La lógica de la investigación etnográfica*. Madrid: Trotta.

Wahlström, B., 2011. Organisational learning – Reflections from the nuclear industry. *Safety Science* 49, 65-74.

Weick, K., 1979. *The social psychology of organizing*. Reading: MA. Addison-Wesley.

Weick, K., Sutcliffe, K.M., 2001. *Managing the unexpected. Assuring high performance in an age of complexity*. San Francisco: Jossey Bass.